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New insights into the 17 β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase type 10 and amyloid- β 42 derived cytotoxicity relevant to Alzheimer's disease

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Abstract

Background The mitochondrial enzyme 17 β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase type 10 (HSD10) is implicated in neurodegenerative disorders, particularly Alzheimer's disease (AD), through its interplay with the amyloid- β peptide (A β). However, its independent pathological role in AD remains unclear.

Methods To explore the individual effects of HSD10 and amyloid precursor protein (APP) overexpression (including the A β 42-generating APP_{Swe/Ind} variant), monoclonal HEK293 cell lines were developed. Cellular fitness was evaluated by measuring ATP levels, cell viability, and cytotoxicity measurements under glucose and galactose culture conditions. Mitochondrial metabolic changes were analysed using mitochondrial electron flow measurements in response to various metabolic substrates. HSD10 enzymatic activity was monitored using a fluorogenic probe, and two HSD10 inhibitors were tested for their ability to reduce cytotoxic effects. Statistical significance was determined using appropriate tests as detailed in the methods section.

Results The overexpression of HSD10 or APP_{Swe/Ind} led to mitochondrial dysfunction and reduced viability, particularly under glucose-deprived conditions. HSD10-driven cytotoxicity was linked to its enzymatic activity and associated with impaired TCA cycle function, reduced β -oxidation, and increased oxidative stress. In contrast, APP_{Swe/Ind} overexpression induced A β 42 production, glucose hypermetabolism, and enhanced β -oxidation. A β 42 also affected HSD10 activity and further amplified its cytotoxic effects. The benzothiazole-based HSD10 inhibitor **34** restored cell viability under both HSD10 overexpression and A β 42-rich conditions.

Conclusions HSD10 and A β 42 each contribute to mitochondrial impairment via distinct metabolic pathways. These findings established HSD10 as an independent pathological factor in AD and support the potential of HSD10 inhibitors, particularly inhibitor **34**, as therapeutic agents targeting mitochondrial dysfunction in AD.

Keywords 17 β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase type 10, Amyloid- β peptide, Alzheimer's disease, Amyloid precursor protein, Mitochondria

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Background

17 β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase type 10 (HSD10, UniProt: Q99714), a member of the short-chain dehydrogenase/reductase superfamily, is a multifunctional mitochondrial NAD⁺-dependent enzyme involved in fatty acid metabolism, isoleucine degradation, and steroid metabolism [1]. Besides its enzymatic activity, HSD10 is also involved in mitochondrial tRNA maturation and its further downstream processing [2–4]. HSD10 protein was found essential for normal mitochondrial function and neuronal development, as mutations in the HSD10 gene impacting the protein's structural stability have been associated with a rare X chromosome-linked inborn error of metabolism which causes rapid and progressive neurodegeneration prevalent in neonatal and infant age [5–7]. The changes in HSD10 levels and/or its enzymatic function are connected with several diseases, particularly with neurodegenerative disorders such as Alzheimer's disease (AD) [1] and Parkinson's disease [8]. In AD, elevated levels of HSD10 were found in affected brain regions, where HSD10 is considered to mediate amyloid- β peptide (A β)-associated cytotoxicity, and this interplay is thought to be one of the possible aspects of AD pathogenesis [9, 10].

In AD progression, the engagement of HSD10 and its interplay with A β results in mitochondrial dysfunction and neuronal destruction [9–11]. A β peptide is the cleavage product of amyloid precursor protein (APP), derived via APP's subsequent amyloidogenic splicing by β - and γ -secretases. A β and its deposits are one of the histopathological hallmarks found in AD patients' brains. A β produced by APP cleavage can range from 36 to 43 amino acids [12]. A β peptide is a normal metabolic product present even in healthy individuals, generated through the physiological cleavage of APP. However, excessive accumulation or altered processing of APP leading to abnormal A β species is associated with AD pathology and neurotoxicity [13]. In relation to human AD brain deposits, the A β 42 long fragment dominates, and its oligomeric forms are considered neurotoxic A β species [14, 15].

Importantly, APP is not only a pathological precursor of A β but also a vital protein with essential physiological functions in the brain. Full-length APP acts as a receptor involved in signal transduction via G-protein interactions [16] and contributes to cell adhesion by binding various extracellular molecules or facilitating intercellular contact [17]. The binding of specific ligands, such as A β , F-spondin, or netrin-1, to the extracellular domain of APP can further modulate its processing and downstream signaling pathways [18–20]. Additionally, studies using APP gene silencing have revealed its role in regulating neuronal migration during early brain development [21, 22]. These physiological functions are particularly

important during neurodevelopment but also support synaptic plasticity and cognitive performance in the adult brain.

The mitochondrial dysfunction, as a consequence of HSD10 and A β peptide interplay, is characterized by elevated oxidative stress, increased reactive oxygen species (ROS) production, inhibition of mitochondrial complex IV, altered ATP (adenosine triphosphate) level, the release of lactate dehydrogenase and cytochrome c from the mitochondria, DNA fragmentation, and increased apoptosis, and results in cell death [9–11, 23–25]. According to the available publications, HSD10 is thought to mediate A β -driven cytotoxicity, probably in a manner where A β affects HSD10 enzymatic function [24–26]. The HSD10-A β interaction was studied using recombinant HSD10 enzyme, resulting in the determination of a dissociation constant of 55.8 nM for A β 42 [10]. Based on the literature, preventing the HSD10-A β interplay and/or modulation of HSD10 enzymatic function offers potential opportunities for drug development [27–29]. To date, several classes of HSD10 inhibitors or inhibitors of HSD10-A β interaction have been published (Fig. 1) [27, 30–36].

However, further development and evaluation of the aforementioned HSD10 inhibitors require a better understanding of their potential to mitigate the HSD10 overexpression-related pathology. Thus, without a thorough understanding of the pathological role of HSD10 overexpression in AD, it is difficult to accurately assess and compare HSD10 inhibitors and their potential as effective therapies. This study hence aimed to describe the effects of individual HSD10 and APP overexpression on cellular fitness, with the main focus on HSD10's role in cytotoxicity development, both independently and in the presence of A β . In addition, the acquired findings were used to develop a novel model for testing HSD10 inhibitors, enabling the scoring of their ability to reduce pathology linked to HSD10 and A β , two critical factors in AD progression.

Materials and methods

Chemicals and compounds

The majority of the chemicals used were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich unless otherwise noted. All chemicals were of the highest commercially available purity. The tested HSD10 inhibitors were chosen from the in-house library of the University of Hradec Kralove, Faculty of Science. The synthetic routes and chemical properties can be found in the published articles [38–40]. All compounds were dissolved in anhydrous dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and further diluted with assay buffers or culture media to the working concentrations to keep maximum DMSO concentration at 2% (v/v) for HSD10

Fig. 1 (A) Representatives of the three main classes of HSD10 inhibitors– benzothiazole derivatives (**34**) [37], pyrazole derivatives (**AG18051**) [38], and steroid derivatives (**D-3,7**) [36]. (B) Representatives of two main classes of inhibitors of HSD10-A β interaction– frentizole derivatives (**5I**) [33] and loopD mimetics (**VC-15**) [34]

activity measurements and at 1% (v/v) for other cell culture experiments.

Cell cultures and HSD10 overexpression or APP_{Swe/Ind} overexpression

HEK293 cells (ECACC Cat# 85120602, RRID: CVCL_0045) were commonly cultured in Dulbecco's modified Eagle medium (Capricorn; DMEM) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (Gibco), 2 mM L-glutamine (Gibco), and non-essential amino acid additives (Gibco) at 37 °C in a 6% CO₂ humidified atmosphere (standard DMEM medium with phenol red). The cells were passaged regularly at 70–80% confluency and routinely tested for *Mycoplasma* contamination (MycAlert Plus, Promega). Cell lines have been authenticated during the preparation of the manuscript [31]. All experiments were performed at a maximum passage number of 15 (the passage number counting started at the time of purchase). Glucose (4.5 g/L) or galactose (1.8 g/L) Dulbecco's modified Eagle medium (Gibco, A1443001) without the addition of phenol red supplemented with 0.11 g/L sodium pyruvate, 10% fetal bovine serum (Gibco), 2 mM L-glutamine and non-essential amino acid additives (Gibco) were used for all cell culture experiments. Expi293 Expression Medium (Gibco, A1435101) was used for Western blot analysis, size-exclusion chromatography, and mass-spectrometry analysis of the conditioned culture medium.

For APP_{Swe/Ind} overexpression, pCAX APP695 Swe/Ind vector (pCAX APP Swe/Ind was a gift from Dennis Selkoe [21] & Tracy Young-Pearse (Addgene plasmid # 30145; <http://n2t.net/addgene:30145>; RRID: Addgene_30145)) was used as a template. The full-length

gene for APP_{Swe/Ind} was PCR amplified and inserted into a constitutive mammalian expression pcDNA3.4 vector using topoisomerase-based cloning, and the insertion was subsequently sequenced. Low-passaged wild-type HEK293 cells (HEK293_{wt}; human embryonic kidney cells) were nucleofected (Amaya Nucleofector kit V, Lonza, nucleofection program Q-001) with 3 μ g of pcDNA3.4-APP_{Swe/Ind} vector plasmid DNA isolated using PureLink HiPure Plasmid MiniPrep kit (Invitrogen). Twenty-four hours after nucleofection, the cells were treated with G418 disulfate salt solution (Roche) at a concentration of 500 μ g/mL in culture medium to select positive cell clones. After several weeks of clonal selection and expansion, several monoclonal cell lines (referred to as APP_{Swe/Ind} cells) were isolated using the limiting dilution method. The APP_{Swe/Ind} overexpression and subsequent A β 42 overproduction were confirmed by immunoblotting using anti-APP and anti-A β primary rabbit monoclonal antibodies (Table 1). For HSD10 overexpression, HSD10 overexpressing cells published previously were used [31]. For the preparation of HSD10 overexpression cell lines harbouring the inactivated catalytic active site of the enzyme (Y168A, K172A) (referred to as HSD10_{mut} cells), the HSD10 DNA was modified accordingly, prepared *de novo* as a DNA string (GeneArt, ThermoFisher), and cloned into the pcDNA3.4 vector. After DNA sequencing verification, the same procedure was followed as for APP_{Swe/Ind} cell line preparation. The final confirmation of the expression level was performed using an anti-ERAB monoclonal antibody (Table 1). No institutional ethical approval was required for this work.

Table 1 Primary and secondary antibodies used for Western blot analysis

Detected protein	Primary Antibody	Secondary Antibody
HSD10	Anti-ERAB Antibody, Rabbit mAb, Abcam, Cat# ab167410, dilution 1:50000	Goat Anti-Rabbit IgG (H+L) Secondary Antibody, Invitrogen, Cat# 31,460, dilution 1:5000
APP _{Swe/Ind}	Anti-Amyloid Precursor Protein Antibody, Rabbit mAb, Abcam, Cat# ab32136, dilution 1:1000	
A β	Anti- β -Amyloid Antibody (D54D2), Rabbit mAb, Cell Signaling, Cat# 8243, dilution 1:1000 Anti- β -Amyloid (1–40) Antibody, Mouse mAb, Invitrogen, Cat# LF-MA0152, dilution 1:2000	Goat Anti-Mouse IgG (H+L) Secondary Antibody, Invitrogen, Cat# 32,430, dilution 1:1000
β -Actin	Anti- β -Actin Antibody, Mouse mAb, ABclonal Technology, Cat# AsC004, dilution 1:20000	Goat Anti-Mouse IgG (H+L) Secondary Antibody, Invitrogen, Cat# 32,430, dilution 1:1000

Western blot analysis

The expression levels of particular proteins in the overexpressed cell lines were confirmed using sodium dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) 10% (APP_{Swe/Ind} detection) or 15% (HSD10, HSD10_{mut}, and A β detection) resolving gel and 4% stacking gel. The protein samples under reducing conditions were subjected to electrophoresis (10 μ g/20 μ g of whole cell lysates from HEK293_{wt}, HSD10, HSD10_{mut}, or APP_{Swe/Ind} cell lines or 14 μ L of conditioned culture media from HEK293_{wt} or APP_{Swe/Ind} lines), subsequently transferred to 0.45 μ m PVDF membrane, and detected using a primary antibody followed by chemiluminescence detection of HRP-conjugated secondary antibody (Amersham ECL Prime). β -actin as a loading control was used for analysis of whole cell lysates. The gel staining was used as a loading control for the conditioned medium analysis.

Primary and secondary antibodies are listed in Table 1.

ATP level and cytotoxicity determination

The impact of overexpression of particular proteins (HSD10, HSD10_{mut}, or APP_{Swe/Ind}) or HSD10 inhibitors on ATP production and the potential cytotoxic effects was tested using CellTiter-Glo Luminescent Cell Viability Assay and CellTox Green Cytotoxicity Assay kits (Promega, G7574 and G8741), respectively. For multiplex measurement, 5×10^3 cells were seeded in 50 μ L of glucose or galactose culture medium per well into a white 96-well microplate with a clear flat bottom (Corning, CLS3903). Cells were cultured for 24, 72, or 168 hr depending on the experiment setup. The assay readouts were measured using the TECAN Spark 10 M instrument following the manufacturer's protocol with minor changes. For cytotoxicity determination, 20 μ L of complete CellTox Green Reagent (mixing 20 μ L of CellTox Green Dye with 6 mL of CellTox Green Assay Buffer) was used in combination with fluorescence readout (Ex/Em = 485/530 nm). For ATP production measurements, 25 μ L of CellTiter-Glo 2.0 Reagent was used, followed by the luminescence-based measurement with an integration time of 500 ms. HEK293_{wt} cells treated with 1%

DMSO only (vehicle control) and 100 μ M valinomycin-treated cells (positive control) were used as the controls.

Viability determination

The protein overexpression effect on cell viability was measured using RealTime-Glo MT Cell Viability Assay (Promega, G9711). The cells (5×10^3) were seeded in 50 μ L of complete glucose medium per well into a white 96-well microplate with a clear flat bottom (Corning, CLS3903). Cells were cultured for 24 hr to allow them to adhere, followed by changing the culture medium to galactose, immediately treating with 50 μ L of galactose medium supplemented with MT Cell Viability Substrate and NanoLuc Enzyme in a final 2X concentration. The treated cells were incubated at 37°C and 6% CO₂ for 30 min, followed by 72 hr of luminescence-based viability monitoring (every 6–12 h) using a Tecan Spark 10 M instrument.

Mitochondrial toxicity determination

A Mitochondrial ToxGlo Assay kit (Promega, G8000) was used to determine the effect of protein overexpression (HSD10 or APP_{Swe/Ind}) on mitochondrial fitness. For measurement, 5×10^3 cells were seeded in 50 μ L complete galactose medium per well into a white 96-well microplate with a clear flat bottom (Corning, CLS3903), followed by 72 hr incubation time. Several control treatments were performed by adding 50 μ L of control-containing media for different time intervals: positive toxicity treatment (100 μ M valinomycin treated HEK293_{wt} cells) for 24 h; positive mitochondrial toxicity treatment (1 μ M antimycin A treated HEK293_{wt} cells) for 90 min; and vehicle control (1% DMSO treated HEK293_{wt} or overexpressing cells) for 90 min. The mitochondrial dysfunction was determined as the activity of dead-cell proteases in combination with ATP level measurement. Complete Cytotoxicity Reagent treatment (20 μ L; mixing of 10 μ L bis-AAF-R110 substrate with 2 mL Mitochondrial ToxGlo Assay Buffer) was added to the cells for 30 min and measured fluorometrically (Ex/Em = 485/530 nm, Tecan Spark 10 M), followed immediately by treatment with

100 μ L 2x ATP Detection reagent and luminescence measurement of ATP levels with an integration time of 500 msec.

Preparation of A β 42-containing medium

To generate a conditioned medium containing cell-derived A β 42, APP_{Swe/Ind} cells were cultured in standard DMEM until reaching approximately 40% confluence. Before medium exchange, the cells were gently washed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) to remove residual phenol red. The growth medium was then replaced with either glucose-containing DMEM medium, galactose-containing DMEM medium, or EXPI293 medium, depending on the experimental condition. The cells were subsequently maintained in a fresh medium for 3–5 days to allow accumulation of secreted A β 42.

After this incubation period, the conditioned medium was collected and centrifuged at 10,000 RCF for 10 min to remove cellular debris. The concentration of A β 42 in the cleared supernatant was determined using the Amyloid beta 1–42 Kit (CisBio, 62B42PEG) based on homogeneous time-resolved fluorescence (HTRF) detection. The medium was then diluted to the desired A β 42 concentration using freshly prepared, non-conditioned DMEM of the same composition (glucose or galactose) or EXPI293. The diluted conditioned medium was used immediately for cell treatment experiments without storage.

A β 42 quantification

To quantify the amount of A β 42 secreted by the APP_{Swe/Ind} cell line, the Amyloid beta 1–42 Kit (CisBio, 62B42PEG) was used. The reaction mixture consisted of an HTRF binding pair of donor and acceptor antibodies (the Human Amyloid β 1–42 Europium cryptate antibody, and the Human Amyloid β 1–42 d2 antibody diluted with Detection buffer to 1X concentration, 2 μ L each) and 16 μ L of diluted sample medium (20 to 50X) or A β 42 standard. The assay mixture was pipetted into an HTRF 96-well low-volume white plate (Revvity, 66PL96005), sealed, and incubated overnight at RT. Two sequential measurements of the FRET signal at 620 nm for Eu-cryptate emission (donor) and 665 nm for the d2 emission (acceptor) were measured, followed by calculation of the 665/620 ratio that was used for concentration determination based on the standard curve approximation.

Cellular HSD10 Inhibition

HSD10 activity in the cellular environment was performed using (-)-CHANA (cyclohexenyl amino naphthalene alcohol) fluorogenic probe [31, 32, 41]. The cells were seeded at a density of 1×10^4 cells per well in 200 μ L of complete glucose medium into a black 96-well microplate with a clear bottom (Brand, BR781971). After

20 hr of incubation, the cells were treated with DMSO only, A β 42-containing medium, or HSD10 inhibitors dissolved in anhydrous DMSO. After 2 hr of treatment, 2 μ L of (-)-CHANA probe was added at the final concentration of 20 μ M. Changes in fluorescent intensities were measured immediately (0 hr) and after 2 hr of incubation. The fluorescence intensities of the reaction product cyclohexenyl amino naphthalene ketone (CHANK) were measured using the TECAN Spark 10 M instrument (Ex/Em = 380/525nm). The HSD10 activity was calculated as the Δ F between 2 hr and 0 hr after (-)-CHANA addition, and the data were normalized between DMSO-treated HSD10 cells and non-transfected HEK293_{wt} controls (using relative response ratio).

Cell metabolic activity changes

To investigate the changes in the cell metabolic activities caused by HSD10 or APP_{Swe/Ind} overexpression, the MitoPlate S-1 technology (Biolog) was used. The 96-well plates preloaded with 31 different substrates (tricarboxylic acid cycle (TCA) cycle intermediates, amino acids, fatty acids, hexoses, and trioses, each in triplicate) were activated by adding 30 μ L of Assay Mix (15 μ L 2x Biolog Mitochondrial Assay Solution; 10 μ L 6x Redox Dye MC; 2.5 μ L 24x saponin (Sigma, #47036) at 960 μ g/mL, final concentration 40 μ g/mL; and 2.5 μ L sterile water) per well and incubated for 1 hr at 37 °C and 6% CO₂. The cells were cultivated for 48 hr before the experiment in glucose or galactose complete media and then plated into the activated MitoPlate S-1 plates at a density of 3×10^4 per well in 30 μ L of 1X Biolog Mitochondrial Assay Solution. The reduction of the Redox Dye mix, which corresponds to changes in mitochondrial electron flow, was read by absorbance (OD₅₉₀) kinetically on a Tecan Spark 10 M instrument at 30-sec intervals for a total of 4 hr after seeding. The data was extracted as Δ Abs per hour from the linear phase of the particular substrate consumption rates.

Liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry analysis

APP_{Swe/Ind} conditioned cell culture medium was loaded to DSC-18 500 mg/mL SPE (Sigma), and bound material was eluted with 20% acetonitrile (ACN) and lyophilized. The lyophilizate was dissolved in reducing LDS buffer (Invitrogen), heated at 70 °C, divided into four lanes of NuPAGE precast gel (Invitrogen), and run by SDS-PAGE. The gel was stained, and visible bands were excised, chopped, and combined from each lane. Protein digestion was done as previously described [42]. Peptides were analyzed using the UltiMate 3000 RSLCnano system connected with an Orbitrap Exploris 480 equipped with a FAIMS interface (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Samples were first loaded onto trap column (PepMap 100 C18, 3 μ m, 75 μ m \times 20 mm) using flow rate 5 μ L/min and

then separated on analytical column (PepMap RSLC C18, 2 μm , 75 μm ×250 mm; both columns from Thermo Fisher Scientific) by running a linear gradient (2% ACN/0.1% FA as phase A; 80% ACN/0.1% FA as phase B) from 2 to 34.5% B in 25 min and from 34.5 to 45% B in 5 min at a flow rate of 250 nL/min. MS analysis was done using data-dependent acquisition with FAIMS CV set to -50 V. MS spectra in the 350–1200 m/z range were acquired at a resolution of 120,000 with a normalized AGC target set to 300%. Multiply charged precursor ions with the minimal intensity of 5000 and not fragmented during the previous 17 s were isolated by 1 m/z window and taken for higher collisional dissociation (HCD) with normalized collision energy set to 28. MSMS spectra were acquired at 30,000 resolution with a normalized AGC target of 100% and a maximal injection time of 54 msec. The sample obtained from < 15 kDa band was further re-analyzed by a longer LC method (linear gradient from 2 to 34.5% B in 85 min and from 34.5 to 45% B in 10 min) and MS acquisition using oscillating FAIMS CVs of -45 V and -65 V. Data were interpreted using MSFragger (v4.1) [43]. Methionine oxidation and N-terminal acetylation were set as variable, and carbamidomethylation of cysteine was set as a fixed modification. Data were searched against the Human Reference proteome database (UniProt) combined with sequences of APP_{Swe/Ind} variant and A β fragment. Proteins were filtered at 1% FDR.

Size-exclusion chromatography

The molecular weight of the A β 42 peptide derived from APP_{Swe/Ind} conditioned medium was determined by size-exclusion chromatography using an NGC Medium-Pressure Chromatography System (Bio-Rad, USA) equipped with a Superdex 200, 10/300 GL column (Cytiva, USA). Phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4) was used as the mobile phase, using the 0.7 mL/min flow rate and 0.35

mL injection volume. The samples were separated into 28 fractions, followed by immunoblotting detection using an anti-A β antibody. The fractions with positive antibody detection were evaluated based on a calibration curve generated using a Cytiva low molecular weight gel filtration calibration kit (28403841).

Statistical analysis

Data were calculated as mean \pm SD from single experiments. Statistical analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism 9 software (GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA). Ordinary one-way ANOVA with Tukey's post hoc test was employed, and a p -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Generation of stable cell models overexpressing HSD10 and APP_{Swe/Ind}

Besides its physiological functions, mitochondrial enzyme HSD10 has been linked to several neurodegenerative diseases, including AD, Parkinson's disease, and HSD10 disease. In AD, HSD10 has been reported to exacerbate the A β pathology, leading to enhanced cell stress and mitochondrial dysfunction [9, 24].

To investigate the role of the HSD10 in AD-related pathogenesis, stably-expressing monoclonal cell lines of human embryonic kidney HEK293 cells were created, overexpressing either HSD10 (referred to as HSD10 cells; Fig. 2A, Supplemental Figure S1-S2) or APP_{Swe/Ind} protein (amyloid- β precursor protein isoform 695 harbouring Swedish and Indiana mutations; referred to as APP_{Swe/Ind} cells; Fig. 3A, Supplemental Figures S4-S5). These cell lines allowed the description of the consequences of individual overexpression in detail.

In addition, a catalytically inactive HSD10 mutant cell line (Y168, K172- mutations in the catalytic active site

Fig. 2 HSD10 overexpression in HSD10 and HSD10_{mut} cells. **(A)** Immunoblotting analysis in HEK293_{wt}, HSD10, and HSD10_{mut} cells. **(B)** HSD10 activity determination via (-)-CHANA to CHANK turnover in HEK293_{wt}, HSD10, and HSD10_{mut} cells (Ex/Em = 380/525nm). Statistical difference: * p \leq 0.05, ** p \leq 0.01, *** p \leq 0.001, **** p \leq 0.0001 compared to the HEK293_{wt} control group

Fig. 3 APP overexpression and A β production in APP_{Swe/Ind} cell line. **(A)** Immunoblotting analysis of APP expression in HEK293_{wt} and APP_{Swe/Ind} cells. **(B)** Immunoblotting analysis of A β 42 production in HEK293_{wt} and APP_{Swe/Ind} cells. **(C)** Immunoblotting analysis of A β 42 secretion to cultivation medium by HEK293_{wt} and APP_{Swe/Ind} cells (non-concentrated sample detection). **(D)** HSD10 activity determination via (-)-CHANA to CHANK turnover in HEK293_{wt} and APP_{Swe/Ind} cells (Ex/Em = 380/525nm). Statistical difference: * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$, **** $p \leq 0.0001$ compared to the HEK293_{wt} control group

[26, 44]; referred to as HSD10_{mut}; Fig. 2A, Supplemental Figures S1-S2) was also constructed to evaluate the importance of the HSD10 enzymatic activity in related processes. The loss of enzyme activity was confirmed using the recombinant HSD10 enzyme and 17 β -estradiol (E2) as a substrate (data not shown).

The cellular catalytic activity of HSD10

In addition to its enzymatic function, the HSD10 protein is a structural component of the mitochondrial tRNA processing complexes [2, 4]. To differentiate between the enzymatic and non-enzymatic roles of the HSD10, the monoclonal HSD10 and HSD10_{mut} cells were assessed for their ability to convert the steroid-like (-)-CHANA fluorogenic probe [41], a specific substrate for HSD10 enzyme in the cellular environment.

The HSD10 cells exhibited elevated conversion of the probe, implying increased HSD10 enzyme activity compared to the HEK293_{wt} (Fig. 2B). In contrast, the HSD10_{mut} cells failed to convert the fluorogenic probe (Fig. 2B, Supplemental Figure S3) despite comparable expression levels of HSD10 protein (Fig. 2A, Supplemental Figures S1 and S2) in both HSD10 and HSD10_{mut} cell lines. These results confirm that mutations in the active site of HSD10 abolish its catalytic functions [10].

Characterization of A β 42 production by APP_{Swe/Ind} cells

Given the central role of A β in the pathogenesis of AD, A β production and release were investigated in the APP_{Swe/Ind} cells (Fig. 3A, Supplemental Figures S4-S5). The A β peptide was detected intracellularly (Fig. 3B, Supplemental Figure S6) and in the APP_{Swe/Ind} cell-conditioned medium (Fig. 3C, Supplemental Figures S7-S8), demonstrating that A β was both produced and extracellularly secreted (in the nanomolar range) by APP_{Swe/Ind} cells.

To verify the production of the specific A β 42 fragment, which is expected as a result of the Swedish and Indiana mutations, two different antibodies for A β immunodetection were used. A signal around 20 kDa was observed for the antibody binding to all A β lengths (clone D54D2), whereas no signal was observed for the monoclonal antibody specific for A β 40 (clone 32A1; data not shown), ruling out the possibility of A β 40 production.

Mass-spectrometry further confirmed the presence of A β 42 by identifying A β 42-specific peptides in the tryptic digest of gel-separated APP_{Swe/Ind} conditioned serum and protein-free media (Supplemental Figure S9A, Band E). Moreover, N-terminal acetylation of A β 42 was identified (aspartic acid, D; Fig. 4A and B), indicating post-cleavage processing of A β 42 peptide and further strengthening the evidence of intracellular A β 42 production. In addition to

Fig. 4 Cell-derived Aβ42 analysis. **(A)** The human APP_{Swe/Ind} amino acid sequence from the human reference proteome FASTA file (Uniprot) used in the proteomic data search. The sequence of Aβ42 is highlighted in red. **(B)** Confirmation of Aβ42 presence in APP_{Swe/Ind} conditioned medium. Proteins isolated from the medium were separated by SDS-PAGE and digested by trypsin. Tryptic peptides specific for Aβ42 (yellow), and not for APP precursor, were identified only in gel band corresponding to < 20 kDa (Band E of Supplemental Figure S9A). **(C)** Western blot analysis of separated fractions of APP_{Swe/Ind} cells' conditioned medium retrieved from size-exclusion chromatography

Aβ42, full-length APP_{Swe/Ind} and APP-derived N-terminal cleavage fragments (sAPPβ) were detected in the conditioned medium, as indicated by the sequence coverage (Supplemental Figure S9B-C).

The oligomeric state of the cell-derived extracellular Aβ42 was determined using size-exclusion chromatography followed by the immunodetection of separated fractions. The most abundant detection of the Aβ42 was revealed under 20 kDa (between 13 and 19 kDa) (Fig. 4C,

Supplemental Figures S10-S11), suggesting the formation into oligomers rather than remaining in monomeric form (4.5 kDa).

Evaluation of the Aβ42 impact on endogenous HSD10 enzymatic activity

The cell-based production of Aβ42 prompted an investigation into whether intracellular Aβ42 affects the enzymatic function of endogenous HSD10. Experiments using

a fluorogenic probe demonstrated that APP_{Swe/Ind} cells have reduced HSD10 enzymatic activity compared to the HEK293_{wt} cell line (Fig. 3D, Supplemental Figure S3). These results indicate that APP_{Swe/Ind} overexpression and the associated A β 42 production are linked to decreased endogenous HSD10 enzymatic activity.

Toxicity and mitochondrial impairment in HSD10 and APP_{Swe/Ind} cells

In AD research, the effect of HSD10 overexpression on cell fitness has been primarily studied in an A β -rich environment [24, 26, 44]. However, HSD10 overexpression may also impact cell fitness through independent mechanisms, which could contribute to AD pathology beyond A β . This study evaluated the effect of individual HSD10, HSD10_{mut}, and APP_{Swe/Ind} overexpression on cellular fitness by assessing ATP levels, cytotoxicity, and cell viability. ATP quantification performed in a complete glucose medium at 72 and 168 hr after cell seeding revealed significantly reduced ATP levels in HSD10 and APP_{Swe/Ind} cells, whereas HSD10_{mut} cells showed unaltered ATP levels. Cytotoxicity was found to be insignificant in all three cell lines when compared to control HEK293_{wt} cells, even at the late interval (Fig. 5A and B, Supplemental Figure S12), and all cell lines remained viable during long-term cultivation in complete glucose medium (data not shown).

Surprisingly, the absence of cytotoxicity in HSD10 and APP_{Swe/Ind} overexpressing cells contrasts with previous reports indicating that A β peptide affects mitochondrial processes and leads to cell viability decline [45, 46]. Since both HSD10 and APP_{Swe/Ind} overexpression are thought to affect mitochondrial function [24, 26, 46], we next assessed cell impairment by altering the major carbon source (galactose instead of glucose). This shift was reported to expose underlying mitochondrial damage not visible in high-glucose conditions [47–51]. Both HSD10 and APP_{Swe/Ind} cells cultured in galactose medium showed a further decrease in ATP levels compared to glucose medium, accompanied by the onset of cytotoxicity as early as 72 hr and worsening at 168 hr (Fig. 5A and B, Supplemental Figure S12). Real-time cell viability measurement confirmed a significant reduction in viable cells for both HSD10 and APP_{Swe/Ind} cells compared to HEK293_{wt} after 72 hr in galactose medium (Fig. 5C, Supplemental Figure S13). In contrast, HSD10_{mut} cells were unaffected by the carbon source change and showed similar growth and ATP levels as HEK293_{wt} cells (Fig. 5A and B, and 5C, Supplemental Figures S12–S13). Findings indicate that HSD10 enzymatic activity is primarily responsible for HSD10-induced cellular damage. Notably, HEK293_{wt} cells exhibited no signs of cytotoxicity in galactose medium, confirming that the observed pathology was primarily due to HSD10 and

APP_{Swe/Ind} overexpression, ruling out galactose toxicity as a potential contributor.

Since the cytotoxic effects of HSD10 and APP_{Swe/Ind} overexpression were observed exclusively in the galactose environment, mitochondrial dysfunction in these cells was further investigated. A mitochondrial toxicity assay was performed by measuring ATP levels (as an indicator of mitochondrial damage) and the activity of dead-cell proteases (as an indicator of secondary toxicity, such as necrosis) in glucose-free conditions. After 72 hr of cultivation in a galactose medium, both HSD10 and APP_{Swe/Ind} cells showed a more than 40% decrease in ATP levels, accompanied by negligible dead-cell protease activity when compared to the HEK293_{wt} cells (Fig. 5D, Supplemental Figure S14). This suggests mitochondrial dysfunction, defined by a decrease of more than 20% in ATP levels and less than a 20% increase in dead-cell protease activity relative to control. These results confirm mitochondrial damage in both HSD10 and APP_{Swe/Ind} cell lines, leading to cytotoxicity and reduced cell viability in a glucose-free environment. Although these findings confirm mitochondrial-based toxicity in both models, the mechanisms underlying the observed toxicities require further investigation.

Metabolic profiling of HSD10 and APP_{Swe/Ind} cells

To gain deeper insight into the metabolic basis of the observed cell pathology, metabolic phenotypes of HSD10 and APP_{Swe/Ind} cells were analyzed using the MitoPlates S-1 assay, which evaluates mitochondrial electron flow (MEF) in the presence of various metabolic substrates. The results revealed markedly different patterns of MEF changes between the two cell lines (Fig. 6; Supplemental Figures S15 and S19), indicating distinct underlying mitochondrial alterations.

HSD10 cells exhibited a broad suppression of metabolism. Specifically, decreased MEF was observed in response to several glycolytic substrates, including α -D-glucose, D-glucose-1-PO₄, D-gluconate-6-PO₄, D, L- α -glycerol-PO₄, and L-lactic acid (Fig. 6A; Supplemental Figure S15), suggesting impaired glycolytic input into mitochondrial respiration. In addition, a reduced MEF response to pyruvic acid and multiple TCA cycle intermediates (Fig. 6C) indicated a substantial disruption of the TCA cycle. Consistent with this, HSD10 cells also showed a marked decrease in basal oxygen consumption, which points to impaired mitochondrial respiration and supports the idea that TCA cycle dysfunction significantly contributes to reduced mitochondrial function (Methodology and Results in the Supplementary Information, Supplemental Figure S20). Furthermore, β -oxidation also appeared diminished, with lower MEF levels in response to various fatty acid substrates compared to HEK293_{wt} cells (Fig. 6B).

Fig. 5 Cell and mitochondrial fitness parameters in HEK293_{wt}, HSD10, HSD10_{mut}, and APP_{Swe/Ind} cells. **(A)** ATP levels and cytotoxicity in HEK293_{wt}, HSD10, HSD10_{mut}, and APP_{Swe/Ind} cell lines 72 hr post-seeding into the glucose and galactose media. Data were normalized between DMSO-treated (1%) and valinomycin-treated (100 μM) HEK293_{wt} cells cultivated in a glucose medium. Values are given as means ± SD from three independent cell culture preparations with four technical replicates (n = 12). **(B)** ATP levels and cytotoxicity in HEK293_{wt}, HSD10, HSD10_{mut}, and APP_{Swe/Ind} cell lines 168 hr post-seeding into the glucose and galactose media. Data were normalized between DMSO-treated (1%) and valinomycin-treated (100 μM) HEK293_{wt} cells cultivated in a glucose medium. Values are given as means ± SD from three independent cell culture preparations with four technical replicates (n = 12). **(C)** Viability of HEK293_{wt}, HSD10, HSD10_{mut}, and APP_{Swe/Ind} cell lines monitored for 72 hr cultivation in galactose medium. Values are given as means ± SD from three independent cell culture preparations with three technical replicates (n = 9). **(D)** Mitochondrial toxicity in HEK293_{wt}, HSD10, and APP_{Swe/Ind} cell lines 72 hr post-seeding into galactose medium. Data were normalized between DMSO-treated (1%) and valinomycin-treated (100 μM) (for dead-cells protease activity) or antimycin A-treated (1 μM) (for ATP levels measurements) HEK293_{wt} cells cultivated in galactose medium. Values are given as means ± SD from three independent cell culture preparations with four technical replicates (n = 12). SD: standard deviation. Statistical difference for ATP quantity and ATP levels: *p ≤ 0.05, **p ≤ 0.01, ***p ≤ 0.001, ****p ≤ 0.0001 compared to the HEK293_{wt} control group cultivated in glucose or galactose medium. Statistical difference for cytotoxicity and dead-cell protease activity: #p ≤ 0.05, ##p ≤ 0.01, ###p ≤ 0.001, ####p ≤ 0.0001 compared to the HEK293_{wt} control group cultivated in glucose or galactose medium

Fig. 6 The mitochondrial electron flow changes (corresponding to metabolic changes) in HEK293_{wt}, HSD10, and APP_{Swe/Ind} cells measured by absorbance (OD₅₉₀) using MitoPlate S-1 assay. Substrate consumption rates were expressed as ΔAbs/hour from the linear phase. Conversion of cytoplasmic substrates (A), fatty acid metabolism substrates (B), TCA cycle substrates (C), and other substrates (D) in HEK293_{wt}, HSD10, and APP_{Swe/Ind} cells. Values are given as means ± SD from three independent cell culture preparations with one technical replicate (n = 3). SD: standard deviation. Statistical difference: *p ≤ 0.05, **p ≤ 0.01, ***p ≤ 0.001, ****p ≤ 0.0001 compared to the HEK293_{wt} control group

In contrast, APP_{Swe/Ind} cells displayed an overall increase in MEF in response to several glycolytic substrates, such as α-D-glucose, D-glucose-1-PO₄, D-gluconate-6-PO₄, and L-lactic acid (Fig. 6A), indicating an

apparent enhancement of glycolytic metabolism. For β-oxidation substrates, these cells showed increased MEF levels, suggesting upregulation of fatty acid metabolism (Fig. 6B). Regarding the TCA cycle, APP_{Swe/Ind}

cells exhibited variable, substrate-specific MEF changes (Fig. 6C), indicating a more selective and less globally impaired influence on TCA cycle activity compared to HSD10 cells.

Interestingly, both cell lines demonstrated increased MEF in response to tryptamine (Fig. 6D), particularly after cultivation in glucose-containing media, suggesting enhanced monoamine oxidase (MAO) activity. This effect was more pronounced in APP_{Swe/Ind} cells. Since elevated MAO activity is associated with increased ROS production [52], a phenomenon observed in AD [53, 54], it may contribute to the downstream oxidative stress and neuroinflammatory responses implicated in disease progression.

Impact of cell-derived Aβ42 on HSD10 enzymatic activity and cytotoxicity in HSD10 cells

Most studies on Aβ have used synthetic peptides [44, 55], but these do not fully capture the complexity of naturally occurring Aβ. In this study, we used cell-derived Aβ42 from the APP_{Swe/Ind} cells to better reflect the physiological conditions found in AD. We aimed to explore how cell-derived Aβ42 affects HSD10 activity and contributes to HSD10-driven cytotoxicity.

To investigate the impact of cell-derived Aβ42 on HSD10 activity, APP_{Swe/Ind} conditioned glucose medium (as a source of Aβ42) was prepared and used for the treatment of HSD10 cells. The treatment in glucose conditions significantly reduced HSD10 activity (Fig. 7B), as measured by a fluorogenic probe, with an IC₅₀ value of

7.6 nM (Fig. 7A). These findings demonstrate that cell-derived Aβ42 effectively reduces HSD10 activity and can be used as an effective Aβ preparation.

To assess the effects of cell-derived Aβ42 on cell fitness, a fresh conditioned galactose medium containing Aβ42 was prepared and used for the treatment of HSD10 and HEK293_{wt} cells. After 72 hr of exposure to 7.6 nM Aβ42 in this galactose medium, both cell lines exhibited decreased ATP levels and increased cytotoxicity (Fig. 7C, Supplemental Figure S16). Specifically, in HEK293_{wt} cells, there was a 23% decrease in ATP levels and a 14% increase in cytotoxicity noted. The HSD10 cells exposed to cell-derived Aβ42 exhibited a further 10% reduction in ATP levels, with an additional 7% increase in cytotoxicity compared with untreated HSD10 cells.

These results suggest that cell-derived Aβ42 impacts HSD10 enzymatic activity and exacerbates the cytotoxic effects associated with HSD10 overexpression, providing further evidence of the role of Aβ in modulating HSD10-driven toxicity.

HSD10 inhibitors' impact on cell viability and HSD10 activity

The concept of HSD10 inhibition as a potential treatment for HSD10 overexpression associated with Alzheimer's disease pathology was introduced many years ago [10, 24, 38, 44]. To study the effects of cellular HSD10 inhibition in the context of reducing HSD10-driven pathology, two nanomolar HSD10 inhibitors with different mechanisms of inhibition were employed: the irreversible inhibitor

Fig. 7 The effects of cell-derived Aβ42 treatment. (A) HSD10 inhibition in the cellular environment. The IC₅₀ determination of cell-derived Aβ42 using (-)-CHANA fluorogenic probe in HSD10 cells in glucose medium. Values are given as means ± SEM from three cell culture preparations with three technical replicates (n = 9). (B) Dose-response curve showing inhibition of HSD10 activity in HSD10 cells by cell-derived Aβ42, measured using the fluorogenic probe (-)-CHANA. Cells were treated with Aβ42 at concentrations ranging from 0 to 9 nM in a glucose medium. Values are given as means ± SEM from three cell culture preparations with three technical replicates (n = 9). (C) ATP levels and cytotoxicity in HEK293_{wt} and HSD10 cells performed 72 hr post-seeding into galactose medium containing 7.6 nM cell-derived Aβ42. Data were normalized between DMSO-treated (1%) and valinomycin-treated (100 μM) HEK293_{wt} cells cultivated in galactose medium. Values are given as means ± SD from three independent cell culture preparations with three technical replicates (n = 9). SD: standard deviation. Statistical difference for ATP quantity: *p ≤ 0.05, **p ≤ 0.01, ***p ≤ 0.001, ****p ≤ 0.0001 compared to the untreated HEK293_{wt} or HSD10 control group. Statistical difference for cytotoxicity: #p ≤ 0.05, ##p ≤ 0.01, ###p ≤ 0.001, ####p ≤ 0.0001 compared to the untreated HEK293_{wt} or HSD10 control group

A HSD10 inhibition		B Cytotoxicity			
Inhibitor	IC ₅₀ (μM) ± SEM	Inhibitor	% of Cytotoxicity ± SD		
			1 μM	10 μM	20 μM
AG18051	0.187 ± 0.028	AG18051	1.23 ± 1.40	0.24 ± 1.73	2.64 ± 3.46
34	4.261 ± 0.495	34	0.00 ± 1.07	0.00 ± 3.34	1.15 ± 1.24

Fig. 8 Inhibitors **AG18051** and **34** characterizations. **(A)** HSD10 inhibition in the cellular environment. The IC₅₀ determination of inhibitors **AG18051** and **34** using (-)-CHANA fluorogenic probe in HSD10 cells in glucose medium. Values are given as means ± SEM from three cell culture preparations with three technical replicates ($n=9$). **(B)** Cytotoxicity in HEK293_{wt} after 48 hr of treatment with **AG18051** or inhibitor **34** (1–20 μM) in galactose medium. Data were normalized between DMSO-treated (1%) and valinomycin-treated (100 μM) HEK293_{wt} cells cultivated in galactose medium. Values are given as means ± SD from two independent cell culture preparations with four technical replicates ($n=12$). SEM: standard error of the mean. SD: standard deviation

Fig. 9 The ability of inhibitors **AG18051** and **34** to reduce HSD10-associated cytotoxicity. **(A)** ATP levels and cytotoxicity in HSD10 cells treated with HSD10 inhibitors (three times the IC₅₀ value; 0.57 μM for **AG18051** or 12.78 μM for inhibitor **34**) were performed 72 hr post-seeding into galactose medium. Data were normalized between DMSO-treated (1%) and valinomycin-treated (100 μM) HEK293_{wt} cells cultivated in galactose medium. Values are given as means ± SD from three independent cell culture preparations with four technical replicates ($n=12$). **(B)** ATP levels and cytotoxicity in HSD10 cells were measured 72 hr post-seeding into the Aβ42-containing galactose medium with HSD10 inhibitor co-treatment (three times the IC₅₀ value; 0.57 μM for **AG18051** or 12.78 μM for inhibitor **34**). Data were normalized between DMSO-treated (1%) and valinomycin-treated (100 μM) HEK293_{wt} cells cultivated in galactose medium. Values are given as means ± SD from three independent cell culture preparations with three technical replicates ($n=9$). SD: standard deviation. Statistical difference for ATP quantity: * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$, **** $p \leq 0.0001$ compared to the untreated HSD10 control group. Statistical difference for cytotoxicity: # $p \leq 0.05$, ## $p \leq 0.01$, ### $p \leq 0.001$, #### $p \leq 0.0001$ compared to the untreated HSD10 control group

AG18051 [38] and the reversible benzothiazole inhibitor **34** [39] (both structures shown in Fig. 1A). Both inhibitors were previously shown to inhibit the recombinant HSD10 enzyme [31]. Here, we confirmed their activity in a cellular environment using the fluorogenic probe (-)-CHANA, determining IC₅₀ values of 0.19 μM for **AG18051** and 4.26 μM for inhibitor **34** (Fig. 8A).

Since both inhibitors were previously shown to have no cytotoxic effects in a glucose environment [31], they were retested in a glucose-free environment to exclude the possibility of hidden cytotoxicity that may have affected the results. Cytotoxicity assessment, 48 hr post-treatment, in HEK293_{wt} cells cultured in galactose medium, revealed no signs of cytotoxicity for either inhibitor, even at concentrations up to 20 μM (Fig. 8B), indicating their safe use in cell treatments.

Evaluation of HSD10 inhibitors in reducing HSD10-driven pathology

Recent HSD10 inhibitors have primarily been tested on recombinant HSD10 enzymes to assess their binding

and inhibitory properties. To extend the understanding of HSD10 inhibition, this study evaluated the potential of these inhibitors to mitigate the pathological effects of HSD10 overexpression. HSD10 cells were cultured in a galactose medium and treated with various concentrations of the inhibitors (ranging from 0.5 to 4 times their IC₅₀ values) for 72 hr.

Both inhibitors, at all tested concentrations, increased ATP levels and significantly reduced cytotoxicity in the HSD10 cells (Supplemental Figure S17). The most effective concentrations were three times the IC₅₀ values (0.57 μM for **AG18051** and 12.78 μM for inhibitor **34**) (Fig. 9A, Supplemental Figure S17), which led to an 18% increase in ATP levels and nearly a halving decrease in cytotoxicity. These findings confirm the ability of HSD10 inhibitors to reduce the pathological effects associated with HSD10 overexpression.

Evaluation of HSD10 inhibitors in an A β 42-rich environment

To further explore the therapeutic potential of HSD10 inhibitors under disease-relevant conditions, their effects were tested in an A β 42-enriched environment, which is known to exacerbate mitochondrial dysfunction and contribute to early neuronal damage in AD [56]. Given that A β 42 exacerbates the decline in HSD10 cell fitness (Fig. 7B), we assessed whether treatment with **AG18051** or inhibitor **34** (at $3 \times IC_{50}$) could mitigate or reverse the pathological phenotype in HSD10 cells cultured in galactose medium supplemented with 7.6 nM cell-derived A β 42, a concentration previously shown to impact HSD10 activity (Fig. 7A).

The results showed (Fig. 9B, Supplemental Figure S18) that treatment with inhibitor **AG18051** had no significant positive effect on improving pathological parameters in the A β 42-rich environment, as both cytotoxicity and ATP production decline remained unchanged upon co-administration of **AG18051**. In contrast, treatment with inhibitor **34** led to a slight, but not statistically significant increase in ATP levels, from 65 to 72%, and a significant reduction in cytotoxicity, from 25 to 14%. Such a phenomenon was also confirmed by another viability assay (using resazurin) (Methodology and Results in the Supplementary Information, Supplemental Figure S21). These findings suggest that inhibitor **34** has the potential to partially reverse HSD10-driven pathology in an A β 42-rich environment and highlight it as a promising candidate for therapeutic development in Alzheimer's disease.

Discussion

This study investigated the individual and combined effects of HSD10 overexpression and A β 42 production on mitochondrial and cellular dysfunctions associated with AD. Using stably expressing monoclonal HEK293 cell lines, we provide new insights into how these two pathological factors contribute to cellular impairments relevant to the disease.

Our study demonstrates for the first time that HSD10 overexpression alone can induce cellular damage, evidenced by impaired cell viability, ATP production, and increased cytotoxicity (Fig. 5). Importantly, this effect depended on HSD10 enzymatic activity, as the catalytically inactive HSD10_{mut} variant did not cause similar impairments. This observation expands previous findings, which primarily linked HSD10 toxicity to its interaction with A β [10, 24, 26] and failed to show the cytotoxic effect of HSD10 overexpression alone in transgenic models [24, 44]. Our data suggest that HSD10 overexpression may independently drive neurodegenerative processes, making it a potential pathological contributor in AD and related disorders. These findings also highlight the importance of tightly regulated HSD10 expression

levels, as increases may disrupt cellular homeostasis and lead to detrimental consequences.

Interestingly, HSD10-induced toxicity was only apparent under glucose-free conditions, which forces the cells to engage mitochondria. This observation aligns with previous reports showing that a glucose-rich environment may mask mitochondrial dysfunctions by using cellular aerobic glycolytic activity. When glucose is replaced by galactose, cells can no longer rely on glycolysis for ATP production and become entirely dependent on mitochondrial function for survival, revealing the hidden mitochondrial impairment [47–51]. This metabolic dependency may explain why previous models failed to detect HSD10-driven cytotoxicity and underscores the critical importance of metabolic context in uncovering mitochondrial pathologies.

Similarly, APP_{Swe/Ind} cells, which produce A β 42, also exhibited cytotoxicity, reduced viability, and decreased ATP production (Fig. 5). Cytotoxic effects associated with APP_{Swe/Ind} and/or A β 42 have been reported previously [45, 46]. Other APP cleavage products, particularly the C-terminal 99 amino acid long fragment (C99), have also been implicated in mitochondrial dysfunction and cellular toxicity [57]. However, in our study, the C99 fragment was not detected in the APP_{Swe/Ind} sample (Supplemental Figure S9), indicating that cytotoxicity observed in this model is unlikely to be mediated by C99 but more probably results from A β 42 accumulation.

Notably, A β 42-induced cytotoxicity in our model also became apparent only under glucose-free conditions (Fig. 5A and B). Importantly, this not only suggests mitochondrial damage due to A β 42 production, but this phenomenon observed in both lines (APP_{Swe/Ind} and HSD10 cell lines) may be highly significant in the context of AD. Aging is associated with impaired glucose utilization [58], a hallmark also evident in AD brains [59]. Therefore, our findings raise the possibility that reduced glucose utilization may act as a triggering factor for developing neuronal defects observed in AD.

The observation that cytotoxicity in both overexpression models (APP_{Swe/Ind} and HSD10 cells) occurred exclusively under glucose-free conditions suggests that mitochondrial damage is a central mediator of the observed cytotoxicity. This mitochondrial dysfunction was confirmed in both cell lines (Fig. 5D). However, metabolic profiling using substrate utilization assay (MEF measurements) revealed distinct underlying mechanisms contributing to mitochondrial impairment in each cell line (Fig. 6).

In HSD10 cells, mitochondrial dysfunction was primarily characterized by disturbances in β -oxidation and TCA cycle activity. These alterations are likely a consequence of increased HSD10 enzymatic activity. HSD10 plays a crucial role in steroid metabolism, particularly

by catalyzing the oxidation of E2 to estrone [27]. E2 has been shown to modulate β -oxidation: its supplementation increases β -oxidation capacity [60], induces expression of β -oxidation-related genes [61], and rescues β -oxidation gene expression deficits in knockout mouse models [62]. Therefore, enhanced HSD10 activity in our model likely increases E2 turnover, leading to reduced intracellular E2 levels. This E2 depletion may contribute to the diminished β -oxidation observed in HSD10 cells. A reduction in β -oxidation also decreases acetyl-CoA availability, thereby limiting substrate input into the TCA cycle [63], potentially explaining the TCA cycle downregulation seen in these cells (Fig. 6C).

Moreover, increased MEF during tryptamine utilization may reflect elevated MAO activity, which in turn could be indicative of enhanced oxidative stress. It is important to note that the MitoPlate assay predominantly measures mitochondrial activity by detecting NADH and FADH₂ production, which mainly reflects TCA cycle function. Thus, the pronounced alterations in the TCA cycle in HSD10 cells may interfere with accurate measurements of glycolytic activity. In this context, it remains uncertain whether the observed MEF patterns truly reflect decreased glycolytic metabolism or are instead artifacts of diminished TCA cycle activity.

In contrast, APP_{Swe/Ind} cells exhibited mitochondrial dysfunction driven by glucose hypermetabolism and partial TCA cycle impairment. These findings are consistent with previous studies suggesting that while late stages of AD are typically associated with glucose hypometabolism, hypermetabolism may occur in earlier stages [49, 64–68]. It has been proposed that cells respond to early A β -induced mitochondrial dysfunction by shifting from OXPHOS (oxidative phosphorylation) to aerobic glycolysis to maintain ATP production [49]. This metabolic adaptation may initially increase glucose utilization but ultimately becomes unsustainable, collapsing towards reduced glucose metabolism in the late stages of disease progression [49, 69].

Our data support previous reports suggesting that glucose metabolism may be upregulated in response to A β 42 toxicity. In APP_{Swe/Ind} cells, this metabolic shift likely acts as a compensatory mechanism to mitigate mitochondrial dysfunction associated with partial TCA cycle impairment, thereby helping to maintain cellular energy homeostasis. Interestingly, β -oxidation also appeared upregulated in these cells, a response that may be linked to the same adaptive process, since a shift from OXPHOS to glycolysis has been shown to promote β -oxidation [70, 71]. Finally, similar to HSD10 cells, increased MEF during tryptamine utilization in APP_{Swe/Ind} cells suggests the presence of elevated oxidative stress.

While further studies will be necessary to assess the activity of individual metabolic enzymes directly, the

significant differences in metabolic responses between the HSD10 and APP_{Swe/Ind} overexpression models strongly suggest that the resulting mitochondrial dysfunction arises through distinct mechanisms.

The secretion of A β 42 into the conditioned medium of APP_{Swe/Ind} cells provided a physiologically relevant model for testing the effects of A β 42. The use of cell-derived A β 42 proved to be an effective preparation with a high capacity to inhibit both the endogenous HSD10 enzyme in APP_{Swe/Ind} cells (Fig. 3D) and the overexpressed HSD10 enzyme in HSD10 cells (Fig. 7A). Moreover, the cell-derived A β 42 appeared to be more effective in inhibiting the overexpressed HSD10 than the synthetic A β 42 preparation used in prior studies [41, 44]. This discrepancy is likely due to differences in oligomerization states. Synthetic preparations are prone to structural variability, complicating their characterization, and were reported to be less potent than cell-derived A β 42, which appears to better mimic the biologically active species relevant to AD pathology [72]. Our results suggest that cell-derived A β 42 used in this study predominantly forms trimers or tetramers, with molecular weights around 13–19 kDa (Fig. 4C), consistent with previously reported highly toxic A β species [73]. Although we cannot exclude contributions from other APP fragments present in the conditioned medium, only A β fragments have been shown to reduce recombinant HSD10 activity to date [10, 74–77]. Nonetheless, if other APP fragments also contribute to AD pathology, using cell-derived A β 42 provides a more physiologically relevant context, reflecting the complex environment in the AD brain where multiple APP cleavage products coexist [78–81].

To explore the functional consequences of A β 42-driven HSD10 inhibition, we examined cellular fitness parameters in HEK293_{wt} and HSD10 cells treated with cell-derived A β 42 (Fig. 7C). The results revealed that A β 42 negatively impacted cell fitness in both cell lines. In HEK293_{wt} cells, the observed decrease in ATP levels and the increase in cytotoxicity were very similar to the phenotype observed in APP_{Swe/Ind} cells (Fig. 5A), although a direct comparison is limited by the fact that A β 42 concentration was not quantified in the APP_{Swe/Ind} cells. Measuring intracellular A β 42 concentration is challenging due to rapid fluctuations in secretion levels, which can complicate accurate measurement [82]. Notably, HSD10-overexpressing cells exhibited an additional decrease in ATP levels and increased cytotoxicity compared to untreated HSD10 cells, suggesting that HSD10-driven impairment is exacerbated in an A β 42-rich environment. Whether this exacerbation is a simple additive effect, synergistic toxicity resulting from direct interaction between HSD10 and A β 42, or if additional mechanisms are involved, remains to be determined. Further studies are required to unravel the molecular

basis of this interaction and its potential implications for mitochondrial dysfunction in AD.

The concept of HSD10 inhibition as a potential treatment for HSD10 overexpression associated with AD pathology was introduced several years ago [10, 24, 38, 44], and multiple classes of nanomolar inhibitors have since been developed [27, 30, 32]. To explore their therapeutic potential in a cellular context, we investigated two HSD10 inhibitors with distinct mechanisms of action: **AG18051** [38], an irreversible inhibitor that forms a covalent adduct with the NAD⁺ cofactor in the enzyme's active site, and inhibitor **34** [39], a reversible benzothiazole-based compound that preferentially binds to the enzyme-substrate complex. Both inhibitors were previously shown to potently inhibit recombinant HSD10 with IC₅₀ values of 89 nM for **AG18051** and 346 nM for inhibitor **34** [31] and to penetrate cells without inducing cytotoxicity [31]. Here, we determined their IC₅₀ values in the cellular environment to be 0.19 μM for **AG18051** and 4.26 μM for inhibitor **34** (Fig. 8A), further supporting their potential translational relevance. While most prior studies focused primarily on **AG18051** [38], this study represents the first comparative cellular characterization of both inhibitors and their potential to reduce HSD10-driven pathology, offering new insights into the therapeutic application of HSD10 inhibition in AD treatment.

The results of our study demonstrated that HSD10 inhibition can mitigate the pathological consequences of its overexpression (Fig. 9A). Despite their differing modes of action, both **AG18051** and inhibitor **34** significantly improved cellular fitness in HSD10-overexpressing cells, supporting that the observed effects are directly attributable to HSD10 inhibition rather than off-target effects. While **AG18051** was previously evaluated in a similar cellular model of HSD10 overexpression [44], the study did not detect cytotoxic effects linked to HSD10 overexpression. However, it did report impaired mitochondrial respiration, which was restored after **AG18051** treatment. In contrast, our study confirms that HSD10 overexpression leads to measurable cytotoxicity and demonstrates that both inhibitors **AG18051** and **34** can reverse this pathology. This also represents the first report on the use of inhibitor **34** in this context.

To extend the therapeutic relevance, we further evaluated the efficacy of both inhibitors in an Aβ₄₂-rich environment (Fig. 9B), as Aβ₄₂ is widely recognized as a key driver of mitochondrial dysfunction and early neuronal loss in AD [56]. While both inhibitors were effective in cells with HSD10 overexpression alone, only inhibitor **34** was able to rescue cellular fitness in the presence of Aβ₄₂. In contrast, **AG18051** failed to reverse the exacerbated phenotype, suggesting its therapeutic potential may be limited in amyloidogenic conditions.

The different effects of **AG18051** and inhibitor **34** raise essential questions about their mechanisms of action. Inhibitor **34** shares structural features with Thioflavin-T (a fluorescent Aβ-binding dye) and frentizole—compounds known to disrupt the interaction between Aβ and HSD10 [33]. Therefore, it is possible that **34** not only inhibits HSD10 but also interferes with HSD10-Aβ binding or acts through direct binding to Aβ₄₂. This additional effect may explain its greater potential in the Aβ₄₂-rich environment. More research is needed to understand these mechanisms in detail. However, our results highlight the importance of testing inhibitors in disease-relevant conditions, not just for their binding and inhibition ability on isolated enzymes.

Overall, our study introduces a new approach to evaluating HSD10-targeted therapies in AD models. Importantly, we provide clear evidence that HSD10 overexpression is directly cytotoxic, supporting its role as a pathogenic factor in AD-related mitochondrial dysfunction. This finding represents a significant contribution to the field, as previous studies had not conclusively demonstrated this toxicity. Furthermore, we identify inhibitor **34** as a promising candidate, capable of reversing HSD10-driven pathology even in the presence of Aβ₄₂. These findings support the idea that targeting HSD10 may help act against mitochondrial dysfunction in AD and reinforce the therapeutic potential of HSD10 inhibitors.

Limitations

This study offers novel and valuable insights into HSD10 pathobiology within an Aβ₄₂-rich environment. However, several limitations should be noted. First, we present a cellular model to clarify the pathological mechanisms associated with an Aβ₄₂-rich environment; however, these experiments were conducted in HEK293 cells, which originate from embryonic kidney tissue and may not fully replicate neuronal metabolism. Nonetheless, these cells are widely used in Alzheimer's disease research [83–86] and exhibit numerous neuronal characteristics, including the expression of over 60 neuron-associated genes such as neurofilament proteins, neuroreceptors, and ion channel subunits [87, 88]. Therefore, to strengthen the data, confirmation would require using another cell line or patient-derived cells. The second limitation pertains to the unknown mechanisms of action of inhibitor **34**, which could reveal more specific interactions involving this compound. In summary, further research is needed to clarify the specific mechanisms of both the inhibitor and the pathological events.

Conclusion

This study provides novel insights into the pathological role of HSD10 overexpression and APP_{Swe/Ind}-driven Aβ₄₂ production in AD. We demonstrate for the first

time that HSD10 overexpression alone compromises cell viability via mitochondrial dysfunction caused by elevated enzymatic activity, with associated impairments in the TCA cycle and β -oxidation. These findings highlight a distinct and independent pathological role of HSD10 in AD. In parallel, APP_{Swe/Ind} overexpression caused mitochondrial damage and triggered a shift toward glucose hypermetabolism, including upregulation of β -oxidation and alterations in the TCA cycle. These changes are consistent with a metabolic adaptation to compensate for the A β -induced cellular stress [49, 69]. Notably, both models exhibited increased vulnerability under glucose-free conditions, emphasizing the importance of impaired glucose utilization in AD pathology [89].

Moreover, we established the use of conditioned media from APP_{Swe/Ind} cells as a physiologically relevant source of A β 42 for *in vitro* experiments. The cell-derived A β 42 modulated HSD10 enzymatic activity and exacerbated HSD10-driven cellular damage. Importantly, this model enabled the evaluation of HSD10 inhibitors, effectively reducing observed pathology. Among them, the benzothiazole-based inhibitor **34** emerged as a promising therapeutic candidate, restoring cell viability and reducing cytotoxicity even under A β 42-rich conditions.

Abbreviations

A β	Amyloid-beta peptide
ACN	Acetonitrile
AD	Alzheimer's disease
APP	Amyloid precursor protein
ATP	Adenosine triphosphate
C99	C-terminal 99 amino acid long fragment of amyloid precursor protein
CHANA	Cyclohexenyl amino naphthalene alcohol
CHANK	Cyclohexenyl amino naphthalene ketone
DMEM	Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium
DMSO	Dimethyl sulfoxide
E2	17 β -estradiol
ECL	Excellent chemiluminescent substrate
ERAB	Endoplasmic reticulum-associated A β -binding protein; former name for HSD10
FA	Formic acid
FADH ₂ /FAD	Flavin adenine dinucleotide
HEK293	Human embryonic kidney cells
HSD10	17 β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase type 10
LC-MS	Liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry
MAO	Monoamine oxidase
MEF	Mitochondrial electron flow
NADH/NAD ⁺	Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide
OXPPOS	Oxidative phosphorylation
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
RCF	Relative centrifugal force
ROS	Reactive oxygen species
sAPP β	N-terminal cleavage fragment of amyloid precursor protein
SD	Standard deviation
SDS-PAGE	Sodium dodecyl-sulphate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis
SEM	Standard error of the mean
TCA	Tricarboxylic acid cycle
Wt	Wild-type

Supplementary Information

The online version contains supplementary material available at <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13195-025-01821-8>.

Supplementary Material 1

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Author contributions

A.H. and M.S. designed the study; A.H., M.S., I.F., and R.A. performed experiments; A.H. and M.S. wrote the manuscript; A.H., M.S., O.B., I.F., L.Z., O.S., and K.M. revised the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Data availability

No datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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